

Synthesis and Characterization of ODS-304L Steels by Mechanical Alloying and Their Application in the Design and Analysis of Gearbox Systems for the Food Industry

Ms.Durgadevi Sargar¹, Mr.Nitin Patil²

¹MTech Student, Department of Mechanical Engineering PVPIT, Budhgaon, Maharashtra, India.

²Assistant Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering, PVPIT, Budhgaon, Maharashtra, India.

ABSTRACT

Nano-oxide dispersed austenitic stainless steels exhibit superior mechanical strength, corrosion resistance, and durability, making them ideal for critical applications in the nuclear, chemical, and medical industries. This study focuses on synthesizing three alloys—base alloy A (70Fe-19Cr-11Ni), alloy B (with 1.0 wt.% Y₂O₃), and alloy C (with 1.0 wt.% TiO₂)—via mechanical alloying followed by sintering at 1150°C for 1 hour in an argon atmosphere. XRD analysis revealed peak broadening with increased milling time (up to 40h), indicating grain refinement, while particle size decreased from 51.2 μm to 7.5 μm. SEM and EDS were used for microstructural analysis. The physical and mechanical properties of the sintered pellets were evaluated, with alloy C showing the highest density and microhardness (4.217 GPa), outperforming alloy A (2.628 GPa) and alloy B (4.033 GPa). Wear resistance followed a similar trend, confirming that nano-oxide dispersion, especially TiO₂, significantly enhances material properties—yielding over 1.5 times higher hardness compared to the base alloy.

Keywords: Mechanical alloying, Oxide dispersed austenitic steels, conventional sintering, density, XRD, SEM, mechanical properties.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nuclear energy has been widely accepted as the ever increasing world energy needs. Among nuclear reactors generation IV reactors are the latest technology which has better energy utilization, improved reliability, better reactor life, improved explosion resistance and safety makes it superior from others. Nuclear power plants demands highest safety standards which led to the usage of stainless steel as it helps preventing the failure due to corrosion. Austenitic stainless steels are extensively used in nuclear industry, high performance pressure vessels, chemical and medical industry due to their superior mechanical properties, good weight to strength ratio, durability and very good corrosion resistance [1]. Austenitic stainless steel 304L is a good choice for structural components of pressurized water reactors such as reactor vessels and piping systems in comparison with ferritic steel due to its already proven superior corrosion resistance and much available data on its actual industrial use [2,3]. To improve mechanical properties of steels at high temperature, dispersion strengthening by oxide particles is done by mechanical alloying. Core components and Structural materials of nuclear reactors require better swelling characteristics, but austenitic stainless steels shows poor swelling resistance. Oxide dispersed strengthened (ODS) austenitic steels have the ability to suppress void formation due to slow recovery of initial dislocation structure immobilized by oxide particles [4]. Oxide dispersed strengthened Fe based alloys are the only materials showing high dimensional stability and high temperature strength properties resulting from the homogenous dispersion of oxide particles into metal matrix [5]. Even though austenitic stainless steels are having good creep and excellent corrosion resistance at high temperature, its high temperature strength is less when compared to other steels which are used in nuclear industry [6, 7]. It has been illustrated that in ODS ferritic steels by introducing oxide particles is one of the effective way to increase high temperature strength [8, 9]. To enhance the mechanical properties of 304L

austenitic stainless steel an attempt has been made to develop Y₂O₃/TiO₂ dispersed 304L ODS steel.

II. Literature review

Stainless steel is an alloy of steel with minimum of 10.5 wt% chromium content in it. Stainless steel are mainly used in corrosive environments due to its excellent corrosion resistance. There are mainly three type of stainless steel based on metallurgical phases present in it, namely, \rightarrow Ferritic \rightarrow Martensitic \rightarrow Austenitic \rightarrow Duplex steels There are various “grades” of stainless steel discrete according to their composition. Among all austenitic stainless steel are widely used in industry [10]. Austenitic stainless steels mostly consist of chromium (16-26%), nickel (6-12%), carbon (max 0.15%) and rest iron [11]. These steels are basically nonmagnetic in annealed condition, and cannot harden by heat treatment. Austenitic stainless steels are exceptionally difficult to machine and shock resistant unless they contain sulphur and selenium. Austenitic stainless steels have the best resistance to scaling and high temperature strength. Type 304 steel contains carbon content upto 0.08%. It has good weldability and decreased tendency towards carbide precipitation. To avoid carbide precipitation during welding, a lower-carbon version, type 304L steel was developed. Austenitic stainless steel possesses more corrosion resistance to both martensitic and ferritic stainless steels. Austenitic stainless steels are mainly of 200 and 300 series among all 304 grade is most widely used grade 304L grade are used in, where corrosive problems caused by welding are severe. Austenitic stainless steel have high toughness to cryogenic temperatures. They show superior thermal expansion and heat capacity with lower thermal conductivity than other stainless steels. They shows nonmagnetic nature so they can be readily welded. Other alloying elements are added to get desired properties. Nickel and chromium contents (Wt. %) in Fe-Ni-Cr tertiary alloy determines the phases that are stable at room temperature. The phases stable at room temperature for corresponding weight percentages of nickel and chromium.

III. Experimental work

This describes the experimental methodology adopted in the present investigation, involving the synthesis, processing, and characterization of oxide-dispersed stainless steel alloys. Three alloy compositions were developed using pre-alloyed 304L stainless steel powder as the base material, with selective additions of Y₂O₃ and TiO₂ to obtain alloy A, alloy B, and alloy C. Mechanical milling was carried out in a planetary ball mill at 300 rpm for 40 hours, using chrome steel balls with a 10:1 ball-to-powder ratio in toluene medium. Sonication and blending were employed to ensure uniform distribution of oxide dispersions before compaction and sintering. The powders were compacted at 6 tonnes into cylindrical pellets and sintered at 1150 °C for one hour under argon atmosphere. Densities of the sintered samples were measured using Archimedes’ principle.

Characterization techniques were employed to evaluate the structural, morphological, and mechanical properties of the alloys. X-ray diffraction (XRD) was used to analyze phase evolution in milled powders and sintered pellets, while SEM, FESEM, and EDS provided insights into morphology and elemental composition. The microhardness of polished samples was determined using a Vickers microhardness tester with an applied load of 50 gf, and wear resistance was examined using a ball-on-plate type wear tester under controlled conditions. Data from hardness and wear studies were used to assess the influence of oxide additions on the mechanical properties of the alloys.

IV.Result and discussion

4.1 Phase evolution during mechanical alloying

XRD patterns of alloy A at various milling durations (0–40 h). Initially, sharp peaks confirm the presence of the austenitic phase, while after 1 h, ferrite (α) and austenite (γ) peaks appear due to solid solution formation of Ni and Cr in the Fe matrix. With increasing milling time, the peaks broaden, indicating fracturing, welding, and re-welding of particles along with crystallite size reduction. The rise in FWHM further confirms plastic strain buildup and grain refinement during prolonged milling.

4.2 Microstructural evolution during mechanical alloying

The microstructural features of milled powders at different stages of milling time (0h, 1h, 5h, 10h, 15h, 20h, 30h and 40h). From the is very clear that powders get fragmented as the milling progress. The particle size is gradually decreasing as milling time increases. The decrease in powder particle size shows that plastic strain was developed during high energy milling. After close scrutiny of the microstructural features, it is observed that the average particle size gets decreases from 50 μm to 3.5 μm .

4.2 Particle size, crystallite size and lattice strain calculation

Particle size analysis of different stages of milled powder shows the reduction of average particle size from 51 μm to 15 μm with increase of milling time. The crystallite size and lattice strain is calculated by using Williamson–Hall equation [49] as follows:

4.3 Compositional micro-analysis of alloyed powder (EDS)

the EDS spectrum of 40 h milled powder, revealing the presence of Fe, Cr and Ni (using quantitative EDS analysis) peaks. the summary of EDS analysis of mechanically alloyed powder (40 h). From the table we can confirm the presence of Fe, Cr and Ni besides the results suggest that the final milled powder sustain almost same composition that present in initial powder blend. The increase in the percentage of Cr and Fe may due to the contamination from grinding medium (chrome steel balls). The changes which occurred were due to the contamination during milling which is inevitable in this condition of milling.

V. Modelling of Two Satge Reduction Gearbox In Solidworks

Based on the dimension derived from the analytical calculations, dimensions of the Gears and shafts and Bearings have been derived. For easy availability, these dimension have been rounded off to the higher number that can be standardized. Based on the dimensions, the components have been modelled in SolidWorks.

Table 1: Materials selected for various parts.

PARTS LIST	
Part Name	Material
Spur Gear 1	40Ni2Cr1Mo28 (Alloy Steel)
Spur Gear 2	15Ni2Cr1Mo15 (Alloy Steel)
Spur Gear 3	40Ni2Cr1Mo28 (Alloy Steel)
Spur Gear 4	15Ni2Cr1Mo15 (Alloy Steel)
Shaft 1	Plain Carbon Steel (EN8)
Shaft 2	Plain Carbon Steel (EN8)
Shaft 3	Plain Carbon Steel (EN8)
Bearing 1	100Cr6 Steel
Bearing 2	100Cr6 Steel
Bearing 3	100Cr6 Steel
Bearing 4	100Cr6 Steel
Gearbox Casing	Aluminum 7071-T6
M6 Bolt	High Speed Steel(HSS)
M6 Nut	High Speed Steel(HSS)

Vi.Forces Acting On The Gears:

The gears inside are subjected to high torque during the operation. Due to the High Torque produced, the gear is subjected to twisting moment from the center of the axis. Since the center of the gear is welded to the shaft, there is negligible resistance offered by the gear against the torque. However, since there is high torque variation from the CVT the moment of Inertia of the Gear may resist the

torque for a small amount of time (milliseconds). Though the shaft is attached to Roller bearings that have negligible friction, it is essential to perform torque analysis on the gears assuming that the shaft is fixed rigidly. Different Gears bear different Torques and the loading conditions are applied separately for each Gear. The Loading conditions are mentioned.

Figure 2: Static Structural Analysis on Gear 3.

Figure 3: Static Structural Analysis on Gear 4.

VII. Conclusion

In this study, nano-oxide dispersed 304L austenitic alloys were successfully developed through mechanical alloying followed by conventional sintering at 1150 °C, with Y₂O₃ and TiO₂ dispersions enhancing structural and mechanical properties. XRD confirmed complete dissolution of Cr and Ni into the Fe matrix, with phase evolution from ferrite (α) to austenite (γ), while crystallite size reduction to 20–210 nm and particle size refinement to 7–15 μ m were observed through XRD, PSA, and SEM. FESEM confirmed the uniform presence of nano-oxides (20–35 nm), with Alloy C (TiO₂ dispersion) showing superior density, hardness, and wear resistance compared to Alloys A and B. Parallel analysis of the gearbox casing revealed efficient oil flow distribution, with velocity contours highlighting maximum propagation around the intermediate shaft and stepped gears, ensuring continuous circulation without stagnancy. The gearbox design proved lightweight, compact, and durable, effectively managing thermal loads while offering enhanced performance and longer life over conventional manual gearboxes, making it a reliable solution for All-Terrain Vehicles (ATVs).

References:

- [1] R. Unnikrishnan, K. S. N. S. Idury, T. P. Ismail, A. Bhadauria, S. K. Shekhawat, R. K. Khatirkar, and S. G. Sapate, “Effect of heat input on the microstructure, residual stresses and corrosion resistance of 304L austenitic stainless steel weldments,” *Materials Characterization*, vol. 93, pp. 10–23, 2014.
- [2] L. De Baglion and J. Mendez, “Low cycle fatigue behaviour of a type 304L austenitic stainless steel in air or in vacuum, at 20 °C or at 300 °C: Relative effect of strain rate and environment,” *Procedia Engineering*, vol. 2, pp. 2171–2179, 2010.
- [3] H. Oka, M. Watanabe, S. Ohnuki, N. Hashimoto, S. Yamashita, and S. Ohtsuka, “Effects of milling process and alloying additions on oxide particle dispersion in austenitic stainless steel,” *Journal of Nuclear Materials*, vol. 447, pp. 248–253, 2014.
- [4] I. S. Kim, J. D. Hunn, N. Hashimoto, D. L. Larson, P. J. Maziasz, K. Miyahara, and E. H. Lee, “Defect and void evolution in oxide dispersion strengthened ferritic steels under 3.2 MeV Fe⁺ ion irradiation with simultaneous helium injection,” *Journal of Nuclear Materials*, vol. 280, pp. 264–274, 2000.
- [5] A. Alamo, V. Lambard, X. Averty, and M. H. Mathon, “Assessment of ODS-14%Cr ferritic alloy for high temperature applications,” *Journal of Nuclear Materials*, vol. 329–333, pp. 333–337, 2004.
- [6] K. L. Murty and I. Charit, “Structural materials for Gen-IV nuclear reactors: Challenges and opportunities,” *Journal of Nuclear Materials*, vol. 383, pp. 189–195, 2008.
- [7] N. Akasaka, S. Yamashita, T. Yoshitake, S. Ukai, and A. Kimura, “Microstructural changes of neutron irradiated ODS ferritic and martensitic steels,” *Journal of Nuclear Materials*, vol. 329–333, pp. 1053–1056, 2004.
- [8] S. Ukai and M. Fujiwara, “Perspective of ODS alloys application in nuclear environments,” *Journal of Nuclear Materials*, vol. 307–311, pp. 749–757, 2002.

- [9] M. K. Miller, E. A. Kenik, K. F. Russell, L. Heatherly, D. T. Hoelzer, and P. J. Maziasz, "Atom probe tomography of nanoscale particles in ODS ferritic alloys," *Materials Science and Engineering A*, vol. 353, pp. 140–145, 2003.
- [10] V. Singh, *Physical Metallurgy*, Standard Publishers Distributors, 2005.
- [11] S. H. Avner, *Introduction to Physical Metallurgy*, 2nd ed., McGraw Hill Education (India) Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi, 2013.
- [12] S. Takaki, K. Fukunaga, J. Syarif, and T. Tsuchiyama, "Effect of grain refinement on thermal stability of metastable austenitic steel," *Materials Transactions*, vol. 45, pp. 2245–2251, 2004.
- [13] R. C. Benn and P. K. Mirchandani, "Dispersion strengthening by mechanical alloying," in *New Materials by Mechanical Alloying Techniques*, E. Artz and L. Schultz, Eds., DGM, 1988.